

A smart-sensing AI-driven platform for scalable, low-cost hydroponic units

D3.1 GOhydro Data Platform

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present report provides an overview of the GOhydro Data Platform and the respective architectural and technical choices for implementing it. The drivers for defining the platform were the general requirements for the envisioned hydroponic unit solution, the sensing solutions defined in the context of WP2, and the data specifications as elicited from the recipe analysis carried out in the context of WP1.

Within the report, the architecture for the GOhydro data platform and its main components is presented and described, while the technologies and frameworks comprising the GOhydro software stack are specified. As the experimental piloting over the platform and the data it generates evolves, more specific methodological solutions will emerge and will be incorporated in the platform. Accordingly, iterative updates on the documentation accompanying the platform's software will be applied and made available via the repositories hosting the platform's codebase.

1 INTRODUCTION

GOhydro aims to develop a cost-efficient smart-sensing ICT platform capable of monitoring the crops' health and nutrient content of hydroponically cultivated microgreens in order to optimize the cultivation process and allow the harvest of the best possible products in any hydroponic installation. In the bigger picture, the project aspires to culminate in the production of a radical platform that will be a shifting paradigm of how AI-driven technological innovation can become an affordable, accessible-by-all and user-friendly tool applicable to all forms of urban farming.

Towards this objective, data management and analysis is crucial for the accurate, timely and secure production and presentation of insights to the grower, via easy to use interfaces. In this context, WP3 aims to put in place the infrastructure that will realise the data storage and analytics functions required by the platform, develop, train and deploy the AI components that will power the recommendation and decision support features, and build the user-facing applications that will provide access to the data collected from a GOhydro installation along with the recommendations to the human managing the installation.

D3.1 deals with the design and development of the data infrastructure that will fulfil the aforementioned data requirements. The data platform is built using established and well-supported blockchain frameworks, over which the data ingestion, organisation, indexing and searching functionalities required by the project are applied. The deliverable also entails the implementation of the API mechanisms that will allow the usage of the platform through client apps, like the GOHYDRO mobile application.

The present report summarizes the architectural and technical choices for implementing and deploying the platform, in accordance with the requirements posed by the scientific analysis of hydroponic growing and the data provided by the sensing solutions integrated in the GOhydro unit.

2 DATA PLATFORM ARCHITECTURE

2.1 ARCHITECTURAL DESIGN

The overall architecture of the data platform is depicted in Figure 1 and analysed below.

Figure 1: GOhydro Data Platform Architecture

As discussed in the relevant deliverable D2.1, the communication point with the hydroponic installation is the Communication and Storage Unit (CSU) incorporated in the installation. The CSU collects data from all sensing nodes included in a given installation and exposes via the appropriate APIs the collected data for further processing.

The data collected by the CSU are sent as JSON objects in the Quantum platform to undergo further analysis by the Quantum Pipelines for Pre-processing and Analysis. Communication between the pipeline components is implemented through the use of an Apache Kafka infrastructure for message passing via a message bus monitored by all components. The components included in the pipeline are described in the following subsection.

2.2 CORE PLATFORM COMPONENTS

2.2.1 Pre-processing Pipeline

The pre-processing modules of the platform will be responsible for the preparation of the incoming data streams before further analysis is possible. On the one hand, the components deal with the identification and annotation/elimination of outlier measurements and identification of gaps in measurement timeseries. On the other hand, harmonization components are responsible for transforming the input data in the representation that will be used for ingesting them in the appropriate persistent storage mechanism from the ones described in the relevant section.

2.2.2 AI Pipeline

The AI Pipeline encapsulates all modules responsible for the analysis of the incoming data towards producing predictions and recommendations for optimizing cultivation in the hydroponic unit. The modules are organised under a workflow that facilitates their re-training in timely intervals as more data and analyses become available, minimising the effort for training, validating and re-deploying the trained models.

2.2.3 Persistence Layer

The GOhydro persistence layer incorporates three different storage technologies, to serve different data functions and requirements for the operation of the platform.

A **Relational Database** solution (MySQL) is used for storing platform-specific data for operations like user management, device registration and status monitoring, etc. A **NoSQL Database** (MongoDB) is used for storing the raw measurement timeseries as delivered by the CSU and exported by the pre-processing pipeline. Finally, a **ledger infrastructure** based on the Hyperledger Fabric platform is used for installation-bound analytics and processed data, to ensure security and history immutability and preservation.

2.2.4 GOhydro API

Data and Analysis Results are exposed via an Authorization-enable REST API, in order to ensure controlled access to the data by the GOhydro mobile application and third-party tools in the future. The API is implemented in PHP, using the Laravel framework.

3 CONCLUSIONS & NEXT STEPS

The report serves as an informative document accompanying the GOhydro data platform prototype. Consequently, it aims to provide a high-level description of the GOhydro technologies, with detailed documentation on the individual components being available via online public repositories or dedicated documentation websites (especially in the case of the GOhydro API). As technical provisions mature, the report will incorporate links to the online resources that will provide further specifications and usage guidelines for the platform, its public APIs and its accompanying applications.

The immediate next steps in the context of WP3 is the setup of the sensing nodes and CSU on the hydroponic unit installation in Greece and the development of CSU connectivity modules. The development of the CSU API for communicating with Quantum and the respective customisation and configuration of Quantum's processing layer components will follow.